

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DEKYEM****FIRST NAME: GIFTY****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MS Word 2016

Key concepts:

1. Writing an Academic Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-12)
2. Punctuations in Academic Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-21)
3. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Style Guide in Academic Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-42)

WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I am happy to be enrolled in this course, yet it has been an overwhelming experience to find my way around the various documents presented at the commencement of the program. The course pack (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024) under consideration is a valuable tool to help me get things right in writing academic essays and, by extension, papers that I will write in the program. I am from Ghana, and English is Ghana's official language due to its colonial ties with Great Britain. However, with the influx of international influence, the vocabulary and style have grown out of context.

Over the years of prolonged usage of the English language by the British and non-British, many variants have emerged. I have embraced various English language types and erroneously spoken and written them without scrutiny. By reading the course pack, I have found the errors I have made in mixing British and American English. It is, therefore, imperative to go back to the basics of the English language for good academic writing.

In this response paper, I will discuss the findings I have unearthed in the course pack and the videos on writing academic essays effectively. In this paper, I will discuss five concepts: academic essay writing, using correct punctuation to achieve a high standard in writing, American versus British English, plagiarism, the style guide in writing academic essays, and drawing my conclusion.

2) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

So many factors come into play when writing an academic essay. Due to the high standards required, so much needs to be considered. Essentially, it is a nonfictional exercise that must conform to approved standards. As I have gathered, Euclid University requires essays to be in three main parts: the introduction, the body of the essay, and, at the end, the conclusion. The essay's body may have subheadings depending on the length of writing and the complexity of the subject matter.

I have learned that writing an academic paper requires that I hasten slowly. There is a need to allow plenty of time for the assignment. Allowing plenty of time will ensure adequate time to read and research the subject area, organize my thoughts, and formulate appropriate topics unless the University assigns a specific topic. Throughout the essay, I focus on answering the question formulated or the task at hand. While reading and putting my thoughts together, I must organize the researched materials to give credit to the writers whose knowledge I have benefited from by citing and referencing appropriately, lest I fall into a grave error of plagiarism with its attendant sanctions.

My research will allow me to showcase the knowledge I have acquired in the subject area in answering the topic question or developing my argument. Logically arguing the salient points in the essay will give a flawless flow and engage the reader. The best strategy I have discovered is to conclude the essay's body before writing the introduction and conclusion. The content of the introduction will enable me to walk the reader through what he or she is to expect in the body of the paper. In conclusion, I will give a general overview of the paper and my impressions as to whether or not my findings support the subject matter amply.

3) PUNCTUATIONS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

The course pack is insightful. It drew my attention to the essentials of punctuation in academic writing. The authors of the course pack advise that, as a general rule, the writer must resort to little punctuation to retain the meaning of a sentence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16). I had an absolute understanding of the use of apostrophes and where to place them to get the desired result in meaning. I identified mistakes I had made in the past, and by learning, I will not repeat them. I also uncovered the effects of types of brackets when put around words or sentences. Efficiently using bullet points, colons, semi-colons, commas, dashes, ellipses, exclamation marks, question marks, quotation marks, and full stops enhances the quality and understanding of academic writing. I must confess that although I had used ellipsis in writing, I just found its name. The correct use of punctuation in academic writing is vital.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I observed that although the English language originated in Britain, particularly England, its wide usage by Americans has taken a formidable space in the world, as rightly pointed out by the authors of the course pack. Today, I see two major variants of the English language, namely American and British English. The two variants are mainly similar, yet significant differences I discovered from the course pack tell the two apart.

I have taken note of the differences between British and American English as elicited by the authors of the course pack. Differences exist in pronouncing the exact words in British and American English; however, some words with the same meaning are spelled differently in British and American English. In American and British English, some words have the same meaning but have different spellings, whereas some words are the same yet have different meanings. Date writing presents differences between British and American English. Whereas the British will write the date starting with the day, month, and year, the American English will write the date starting with the month followed by the day and year. Further differences exist in pluralized adjectives and punctuations in formal and informal settings.

This elucidation has cleared the mix-ups of the two English language types. Euclid University recommends using American English for its students, although British English will equally be accepted (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41). I will chart my course in writing good academic essays by sticking to the American version, as Euclid University endorses. The authors of the course pack did an excellent job of drawing my attention to this anomaly perpetrated by writers such as myself. Writing from an informed position, I can write better academic essays.

5) PLAGIARISM

Cleenewerck and Gulma define plagiarism as when a writer uses source information without acknowledging the author of the said information (34). Tracing the history of plagiarism will elucidate the seriousness of the offense. Plagiarism derives from the Latin word "*plagiarius*" meaning kidnapper. Therefore, any person who plagiarizes another's work assumes the character of a "kidnapper" in the academic world. Merriam-Webster Unabridged Online Dictionary defines plagiarize as: "to copy and pass off (the expression of ideas or words of another) as one's own: use (another's work) without crediting the source." (2024) Accessed 06/04/2024 (<<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/plagiarize#legalDictionary>>) Plagiarism remains an unpardonable sin in academic writing, attracting dire sanctions. However, many do not know what constitutes plagiarism and fall victim to it. Whether committed intentionally or unintentionally brings one's integrity into question. For clarity, Cleenewerck and Gulma gave examples of plagiarism as follows:

Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism.

Quotations are easy to identify as another person's work, but paraphrasing someone else's work or taking another's idea often goes without due consideration. The clarity is helpful, and I need to keep my eyes on the examples of plagiarism so that I do not plagiarize another's work. The only way to unfetter myself from plagiarism is to give credit when due by properly citing and referencing persons whose knowledge I have used in my work. I will credit persons whose work I use with in-text citations, endnotes, or bibliography. I now know that when information is common knowledge, I need not cite the author or source (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2014, 37).

Introduction to applications like Zotero made it easy for me to organize and insert research sources in this paper. Grammarly Premium provided by Euclid University at no cost to students, is an invaluable tool that sharpened my writing skills by providing appropriate prompts for corrections and checking plagiarism scores.

6) STYLE GUIDE IN ACADEMIC WRITING

Cleenewerck and Gulma made me understand what a style guide is, what constitutes a style guide, and the need to stick with a particular one. A style guide is a way of adopting a writing style consistently in a written work (2024, 41). Many internationally recognized styles exist, but Euclid University recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) to its students. The Chicago Rules and Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Turabian 1996) guide how books and research papers are formatted. The Chicago Rules and Turabian Styles mean the same thing; writers cite the names interchangeably.

The choice of writing style largely depends on the field of the subject matter, such as academic, business, or technical writing. It would need the requisite writing style to venture into academic writing. The authors of the course pack teach that a style guide is needed when more than one person is contributing to a publication, for instance, to ensure coherency and consistency (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 42). Writing style is crucial as it defines a writer's work. I find from reading the course pack that writing style entails more than choosing a particular style guide from a drop-down menu. According to the authors (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41-42), writing styles entail but are not limited to the following:

Preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK v US, for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences (active v passive), structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists, trademark and branding considerations.

Although the above constitute writing styles, the list is inexhaustive. The Chicago Rules, for instance, opts for Merriam-Webster's dictionary for spelling and forms of plural

words to promote consistency (CMS 2003, 278). Cleenewerck and Gulma discussed extensively examples of what the Turabian style requires in terms of the use of abbreviations, when to use capitalization in writing, how to use compound words, italics, quotation marks, numbers, quotations, and formatting a page in writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 44–50). The course pack also gives detailed instructions and examples on heading levels and when to use them, footnotes, headings and lists, bibliography, tables, and endnotes (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 51–57).

A writing style does not only have to do with citations and referencing; it entails more than that. These are the foundations upon which successful academic writers formulate their writings. Therefore, I should strictly comply with the Turabian writing style to meet the Euclid University requirements. By adhering to the recommended writing style, I will not only satisfy the requirements of the program I have embarked upon, but my writings will also stand out as scholarly works.

7) **CONCLUSION**

The doctorate program is arguably the highest level of education with attendant excellent writing skills. The ACA-401D course is, therefore, helpful in ensuring the proper foundation is present upon which students can build their writing skills during the doctorate program and life after. The course pack is handy as it teaches and brings awareness to wrong practices, such as mixing American and British English and improper citations in writing. Through the course pack, Euclid University has put its students on notice that it frowns on plagiarism. I have established that there is a whole protocol for academic writing which ought to be learned and implemented. With the immense knowledge I have acquired in the course pack, I can only improve in academic writing.

REFERENCE LIST

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.